

OPEN-PIT TIME SCALE OPTIMISATION IN A TRUCK SCHEDULING PROBLEM

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ABSTRACT. In the present economic situation, the open-pit mining processes require flexible solutions for achieving the set goals. The aim of the study is to consider a comprehensive mathematical model for a short and long term open-pit mine optimisation in a truck scheduling problem. The model can be applied in different situations with various number of units and trajectories depending on the landscape of the area in question. Significant amount of parameters modulating the discussed processes is analysed.

Keywords: time scale optimisation, truck scheduling

Introduction

The need to increase the quality and quantity of mineral raw materials requires the use and development of complex mathematical models that take into account a larger number of variables in the open pit mine system. The complexity of these mathematical models requires the availability of qualitative information for the variation of the basic parameters of the mineral raw materials or coal (annual productivity, product prices, ash content, humidity, etc.). Proper collection and storage of information can be a key point in choosing an optimisation method and analysing the results.

In the processes of excavation and digging of the mineral raw materials or technogenic waste different problems emerged, most of which are not included in the plan of the open pit operation (Grigorova and Koprev, 2017; Koprev and Kaykov, 2017). Such short time scale problems, for example, the decision of the engineer to mine or not every next block, need to be solved with the methods suitable for such situations. These methods are different from those which should be used in determining for example the shape and size of the open pit, ore recovery, extent of the deposit, etc.

Long and short-term planning in surface mining determine the optimisation of scheduling problem (Dagdalen, 1986; Osanloo et al. 2008; Amankwah, 2011). While the long-term schedule determines most of the based engineering decisions including equipment selection, maintenance planning, dispatching and so on, the short-term production scheduling is focused more or less on unpredictable difficulties or features in the mining process.

Several studies have examined aspects of the truck scheduling problem (Frimpong et al., 2002; Yang et al., 2006; Chang et al., 2015). Here we study this problem in the long and short-term planning context. We seek to characterise the main difference in modelling when time variable exists.

If we consider the well-known "block model" of planning extractions in open pit mines (Espinoza et al., 2013) (Fig.1), a long-term scheduling (at least several months or years) determines the consistency of the extraction. In that sense, the first and the most important note related to the present studies is determining the time periods that distinguish what are "long" and "short" periods.

Because of the complexity of the truck scheduling problem, a number of software products based on the optimisation linear models have been developed. Most of them are quite applicable when we consider long-term scheduling, but generally results are far from optimal.

Fig. 1. View of the block model (Espinoza et al., 2013)

Motivation

The development of usable mathematical algorithm of the time scale optimisation in the truck scheduling problem is motivated by constantly growing goals of economic profit. The efficient solving of this problem leads to reduction of the transportation cost, and increase in the mine productivity (Alarie and Gamache, 2002).

Trucks are essential element in open pit mine equipment and generally they are used for ore and waste transportation between loading points (L_i) and dumping depots (D_j) (Fig.2 (a)). One important note here is that the location of D_j is relatively constant in time, while the location of L_i varies.

Most of the research related to the problem is focused on the production planning or pit design (Newman et al., 2010), pit limit design and block sequence problem (Wright, 1989; Klingman and Phillips, 1988). Knowing that the long-term schedule can be considered as a vital part of the mine project, we also assume that it is crucial for short term-decisions. Some authors divide the truck scheduling problem into different stages. For example, White and Olson (1992) analyse three phases – shortest path problem, which is the shortest path between all locations L_i and D_j ; the second phase is calculated with linear optimisation of the material stream between L_i and D_j ; and the third – optimisation of the paths.

In this paper we have tried to implement different views of the problem using an extended mathematical algorithm.

Description of the problem

Usually in each open pit mine, there are several loading points L_i and dumping depots D_j . In most cases the number of L_i is bigger than D_j (Fig. 2 (a)). We assumed that each loading point L_i is supplied with only one electric shovel. In other words, one loading point corresponds to one electric shovel. We assume also that the set of accessible trucks T_k are loaded by electric shovels in each loading point and the trucks unload themselves on the dumping points.

Fig. 2. An open-pit mine with (a) a schematic map of the road network (Chang et al., 2015), where L_i ($i=1,..,6$) are the loading points and D_j ($j=1,..,3$) are the dumping depots

When we consider different time periods (time scale optimisation) there are a few notes which are obvious but must be emphasized – one loading point (or one dump) can accommodate one truck at the same time. There are waiting areas for trucks which are not in movement. In the traditional truck scheduling problem, the most important task is to reduce the truck waiting times.

Truck scheduling must be a discontinuous system in which if one unit is not working properly the final result will not be significantly affected.

The mathematical formulation of the problem can be summarized with the following integer variables:

- L_i , where $i = \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ is the set of available loading points, which correspond to electric shovels;
- D_j , where $j = \{1, 2, \dots, P\}$ and $P < N$, are the set of depots;
- T_k , $k = \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$ are the set of trucks that are available.

A truck which is loaded in a given loading point has to transport the material to the given depot. The route is chosen in accordance with the possible transport distance and transport priority.

The following different times periods for the whole process must be included:

- t_i – loading times per truck by electric shovel i ;
- t_j – unloading times per truck in depot j ;
- t_{ij} – time for a loaded truck to move from the electric shovel i to the dumping depot j ;
- t_{ji} – time for an empty truck to move from the depot j to the electric shovel i ;
- t_{0i} – time for a truck to move from the waiting area to the electric shovel i ;
- t_{0d} – waiting time for a truck on a depot waiting area.

The choosing of time periods in which we will analyse the truck scheduling problem actually is the basis of our study. That is why we introduce the time periods' variable as follows:

H – the time horizon considering the problem;

A related variable with H is:

m_i – maximum number of trucks loading by electric shovel i during the horizon period H ;

Integer modelling

For the purpose of the mathematical modelling a few decision variables are introduced:

$$x_{ii} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if truck } T_k \text{ has } t_0 = 0; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$z_i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if truck } T_k \text{ is loaded;} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$u_{ji} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if truck } T_k \text{ has } t_{0d} = 0; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

In the context of the optimisation the best solution of given variables from equation (1) – (3) is when we have x , z and u equal to 1. In other words, trucks do not stand in waiting area.

The sum of all introduced times gives the expected real time of one truck T_k scheduling:

$$t_{exp}^k = t_i + t_j + t_{ij} + t_{ji} + t_{0i} + t_0 + t_{0d} \quad (4)$$

Other decision variable can be introduced concerning truck scheduling in terms of routes:

$$y_{ii} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } T_k \text{ is loaded at } i \text{ and dumped at } j; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Now let's consider the most important times for the purpose of our investigation – waiting times – t_0 and t_{0d} . As far as these times concern one truck T_k , we can introduce the expected real times for waiting in the electric shovel waiting area and the dumping depot waiting area, respectively:

$$t_{exp}^{0} = \sum_{k=1}^N t_0^k = t_0^1 + \dots + t_0^{k-1} + t_0^k + t_0^{k+1} + \dots + t_0^N \quad (6)$$

$$t_{exp}^{0d} = \sum_{k=1}^N t_{0d}^k = t_{0d}^1 + \dots + t_{0d}^{k-1} + t_{0d}^k + t_{0d}^{k+1} + \dots + t_{0d}^N \quad (7)$$

where N is the total number of trucks.

If two trucks are in the same time at the waiting area, the waiting time of the second one is the sum of the waiting time of the first truck, the time of the truck to move from the waiting area to the loading point and the time for loading of the first truck:

$$t_0^k = t_0^{k-1} + t_{0i}^{k-1} + t_i^{k-1} \quad (8)$$

We assume that the time for a truck to move from the waiting area to the electric shovel is the same for all trucks and all loading times are equal:

$$t_{0i}^{k-1} = t_{0i}^k = t_{0i}^{k+1} \quad (9)$$

$$t_i^{k-1} = t_i^k = t_i^{k+1} \quad (10)$$

Using (8), (9) and (10), in (6) we received:

$$t_{\text{exp}}^0 = 2(N-1)(t_{0i}^1 + t_i^1) \quad (11)$$

Similarly, in (7) we have:

$$t_{\text{exp}}^{0d} = 2(N-1)t_j^1 \quad (12)$$

The truck scheduling problem can be formulated as:

$$2(N-1) \sum_i \sum_j (x_{ii} t_{0i}^1 + (1-z_i) t_i^1 + u_{ji} t_j^1) \rightarrow \min . \quad (13)$$

The function (13) of the model minimises the sum of the expected real time of the truck waiting on the electric shovel and depot areas.

Several constrains can be added:

$$\sum_k \sum_i x_{ki} = 1, \quad (14)$$

which correspond to the assumption that only one truck can be loaded by one electric shovel at a time.

Similarly, for dumping depots we have:

$$\sum_k \sum_j u_{kj} = 1. \quad (15)$$

$$\sum_k \sum_i z_{ki} = 1 \text{ and } \sum_i \sum_i y_{ii} = z_{ki} \quad (16)$$

are constraints corresponding to the assumption that there is at least one truck at a time that is loaded.

A few other constraints about providing each truck enough time for loading, unloading and traveling time when the truck is loaded and empty can be summarized:

$$t_{\text{exp}}^k - t_{\text{exp}}^{k-1} \geq t_i \quad (17)$$

$$t_{\text{exp}}^k - t_{\text{exp}}^{k-1} \geq t_j \quad (18)$$

$$t_{\text{exp}}^k - t_{\text{exp}}^{k-1} \geq t_{ij} \quad (19)$$

Conclusion

In the present paper, open pit time scale optimisation in a truck scheduling problem have been examined. The formulation of the model is based on the waiting truck time in the electric shovel and dumping depots areas. Several constraints are assumed.

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